

Sandra Ponzanesi – Review of Paulo Lemos and Bruce Robbins’s “Cosmopolitanisms”

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Cosmopolitanism(s) Interrupted

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reviewed by Sandra Ponzanesi

This edited volume reignites many of the incessant debates on cosmopolitanism, its origin, development, and *raison d'être*, not only from difference disciplinary traditions and “worlds” but also from different points in time. The volume is a revisitation of cosmopolitanism, a new take on many of the ongoing debates and *querelles*, while also making headway by reorienting the field of cosmopolitan studies as such. The vibrancy of the field is shown by the work of influential critics in this volume, who do not take the notion of cosmopolitanism for granted but engage with it from positions that are both critical and creative. These engagements show how the notion or the ideal of cosmopolitanism is far from being obsolete but on the contrary demands, now more than ever, a deep critical engagement. While critics continue to reiterate the assumption that cosmopolitanism’s appeal lies in its universal principles, there is a sense “The Times They Are A-Changin’” as Bob Dylan would put it^[1], and therefore new realities for new paradigms. The accelerated process of globalization has allowed many of cosmopolitanism’s aspirations to come true (increased international mobility of people and markets, waning borders, and an increase in supranational institutions). Yet the total

deregulation and decentralization brought about by globalization and the associated back-bring the very principles of cosmopolitanism into disarray by challenging the very notions of commonality and shared values, with a resurgence of new, localized identities, nationalisms, and ethnic strife. Therefore, even though the world is becoming increasingly interconnected and shaped by global forces, this does not mean that the world has become more cosmopolitan; the contrary, the challenge of cosmopolitanism remains as prominent as ever, because, as Spivak has phrased it in other contexts, cosmopolitanism is “what one cannot not want” (Spivak 110). To dispense with cosmopolitanism would mean to relinquish our ideal of a common humanity and with it the principle of human rights and an ethical responsibility to fellow humans. Cosmopolitanism, as a notion, has accompanied Western civilization from the very beginning; the term and its meaning have shifted and been transformed through time and context, a resilience unmatched by other intellectual paradigms. From the Stoics to cosmopolitanism in the age of the Anthropocene and cyberspace, the term has evolved, retaining a flexibility as a foundational necessity to continue to exist.

It was with Kant’s *Toward Perpetual Peace* (1999 [1795]) that it reached its most authoritative moment, with the birth of modern nation-states and the moral dilemma of keeping peace to promote effective transnational trade. Cosmopolitanism became a comrade in arms with capitalism, and the many paradoxes of its affirmation constituted by colonialism, imperialism, and slavery, where the mobility of the elites went hand in hand with the forced uprooting and exploitation of others. Cosmopolitanism has, moreover, often been linked only to the mobile elites and privileged, who, through education or financial means, were able to cross languages, and political systems. Kant’s moral ideal of cosmopolitanism was a given for a happy few. The idea of the Grand Tour and Sentimental Journey was not open to lower- and uneducated people. With the decline of the aristocracy and the rise of the enterprising bourgeoisie in the wake of industrialization, the notion of cosmopolitanism underwent a transformation, becoming more embroiled with new technologies of communication (the telegraph, fax, phone) and faster and more accessible forms of transportation (trains, cars, planes). The emancipatory cosmopolitanism started to emerge as an intrinsic aspect of modernity, a modernity that hardly had room for vernacular forms and alternative ideas of culture (Appadurai 1996). In the light of these many transitions, this volume proposes a provocation by considering multiple cosmopolitanisms in the plural rather than offering a single notion of cosmopolitanism. The notion of multiple cosmopolitanisms could seem like a contradiction in terms. But is it really? Cosmopolitanism as a way of thinking, feeling, and acting beyond one’s own particular community has been seen as a universalism of a Western particular. In their introductory special issue on “Cosmopolitanism” that appeared in *Public Culture* in 2000, the guest editors—Carol A. Breckenridge, Dipesh Chakrabarty, Homi K. Bhabha, and Sheldon Pollock—offer the critique of cosmopolitanism’s Eurocentric bias, debating how most cosmopolitan forms

are interconnected with forms of coercion or inequality, such as slavery, colonization, and imperialism. So for them the question is whether it is possible to have a cosmopolitanism that fulfills its promise of universal knowledge, that also foregrounds a noncoercive and egalitarian practice. They open with a disorienting idea of what “cosmopolitanism” is or might be, precluding any normative fixing:

“For one thing, cosmopolitanism is not some known entity existing in the world, with a genealogy from the Stoics to Immanuel Kant, that simply awaits more detailed description in the hands of scholarship. We are not exactly certain what it is, and figuring out why and what cosmopolitanism may be raises difficult conceptual issues. As a practice, then, cosmopolitanism is yet to come, something awaiting realization.” (Breckenridge et al. 2000: 577)

After that open-ended consideration, the guest editors nevertheless circle around a possible misapprehension about the use and abuse of the term: “Cosmopolitans today are often victims of modernity, failed by capitalism’s upward mobility, and bereft of those comfort and customs of national belonging. Refugees, peoples of the diaspora, and migrants and exiles represent the spirit of the cosmopolitical community.” (Breckenridge et al. 2000: 582) The guest editors of *Public Culture* thus move skillfully to the use of cosmopolitanisms in the plural, distinguishing between the “other” forms of cosmopolitanisms that have remained in the shadow of the dominant and those that have been cast as “unauthorized forms of cosmopolitanism.” These refer to manifestations of cosmopolitanism among people at the margin of histories who are part of minoritarian constellations, although they might not be so minoritarian in terms of numbers:

“...cosmopolitanism must give way to the plurality of modes and histories—not necessarily shared in degree or in concept regionally, nationally, or internationally—that comprise cosmopolitan practice and history. We propose therefore that cosmopolitanism be conceived in the plural, as cosmopolitanisms” (Breckenridge et al. 2000: 577).

It is an invitation to look at cosmopolitanism beyond the binarism of the local versus global, and also to look for cosmopolitanism outside the dominant schemata, from the Stoics to Kant. This would limit the way we look at and understand what cosmopolitanism can be about. By embracing a look at cultures across space and time, and how they engage with feeling and affect beyond the nation, a new array of possibilities might emerge that are not prefabricated and constrained by Western paradigms. That is also how Paul Gilroy’s notion of conviviality (inspired by Spain’s multicultural Moorish culture of coexistence and cohabitation (*convivencia*) (Gilroy 2004), steering away from multiculturalism without abandoning the aspiration of cosmopolitanism. The guest editors of *Public Culture* conclude that we should first radicalize

rewrite the history of cosmopolitanism and redraw its map by thinking “outside the box European intellectual history” (Breckenridge et al. 2000: 586), and secondly rethink the practices that might allow for new and alternative theorizations.

The volume edited by Bruce Robbins and Paulo Lemos Horta rises to this challenge by e cosmopolitanisms in the plural, not as a fashionable label but as the fruit of decades-lor engagement with the field. Bruce Robbins has written extensively on cosmopolitanism fr different entry points, taking stock of the idea of cosmopolitanism in deep time too, the venturing outside the paradigm of European history (2016); his latest book *The Benefic* with cosmopolitanism from the viewpoint of inequality and is a sequel to *Perpetual War: Cosmopolitanism from the Viewpoint of Violence* (2012). His previously co-edited volum *Cosmopolitics. Thinking and Feeling Beyond the Nation* (Robbins and Cheah 1998) make in not wanting to disentangle the culturalist approaches to cosmopolitanism from its pol relevance, and claims the resurgence of cosmopolitanism as a viable alternative politica Besides the double introduction by the editors themselves, with Robbins responsible for “Actually Existing Cosmopolitanism” and Pheng Cheah producing Part II on “The Cosmo Today,” *Cosmopolitics* contains contributions that are still cutting-edge today. This inclu two full-length chapters by Robbins and Cheah themselves and chapters by contributors Gayatri Spivak, Benedict Anderson, Etienne Balibar, James Clifford, and Anthony Appia also wrote the afterword for the later *Cosmopolitanisms*.

In his own chapter “Comparative Cosmopolitanisms” (already used in the plural in 1998 the special issue of *Public Culture*), Robbins brings forward the institutional entangleme explores the possibility of “comparative cosmopolitanisms” that seek to reconcile a self-academic professionalism with a worldly and political engagement. The book emerged a height of the debate about multiculturalism as merely particularistic and investing in cosmopolitanism as striving towards mutual common ground, extending political practic national borders and including non-citizens as equally valid members of the cosmopolita Robbins is aware of the risks of cosmopolitanism in restricting the space of others, espe the case of what are termed diasporic actions that impact on local politics, and of the da falling outside the security of nation-state regulation. Yet he does not give up on the po that international alliances can offer or the potential of actually existing cosmopolitanis in light of what he phrased as the existence of inevitable paradoxes and contradictions \ field, which nonetheless has not exhausted its purpose. As Robbins writes:

“If we agree that there is ‘no easy generalization,’ don’t we want to retain the right *difficult* generalization?” (Robbins 1998: 251)

The question remains whether in the attempt to safeguard cosmopolitanism, other insur that traditionally may not fall under the aegis of cosmopolitanism, such as transnational diasporic formations, and postcolonial alliances, might be overlooked or unwillingly appr by cosmopolitanism’s historically and theoretically dominant discourse. Yet, it is in the acknowledging of these new intersections between cosmopolitanism and the above men insurrections that Robbins charts the ‘*difficult* generalization.’

Paul Lemos Horta is a scholar of world literature and has worked at length on cultural productions beyond their point of origin, including the cross-cultural collaborations that influenced *The Thousand and One Nights* and its reception. In his book, *Marvellous Thie Secret Authors of the Arabian Nights* (2017) Horta reports on a number of conversation between Europeans documenting the tales and their interlocutors. In this volume, Horta very fine reading of Richard Burton, the British explorer, as a cosmopolitan or counter-cosmopolitan in the light of Anthony Appiah’s engagement with the explorer and transla Appiah’s eyes, Burton is a cosmopolitan who seeks to engage with difference but he is a counter-cosmopolitan because he cannot escape the prejudices of his British upbringing remarks at the end that it might be wrong to attribute Burton’s cosmopolitanism only to exposure to other cultures and attribute his counter-cosmopolitanism only to his inescap Englishness. Rather, Horta suggests, we should take Burton’s counter-cosmopolitan bias part of his self-fashioning as a cosmopolitan. Aware of the long genealogy of the term, I Robbins prefer to engage in their volume with the “new cosmopolitanism” that emerged 1990s. As Pnina Werbner notes, the theories of cosmopolitanism after the 1990s, includ by Breckenridge et al. and Cheah and Robbins, have sought to go beyond an interpretat cosmopolitanism as only universal, open, and above all “Western” in order to include loc rooted, and historically and geographically situated dimensions, “vernacular cosmopolita and local, cultural, and rooted proximities, foregrounding the role of urban space and connectivity of both difference and diversity, and the role of diasporic groups in leading rethinking of the universalism of cosmopolitanism. This implies also inserting a new defi cosmopolitanism from below by incorporating a more “metaphoric designation” that incl various groups of migrants: “expatriates, expellees, political refugees, alien residents, immigrants, and ethnic and racial minorities *tout court*” (Safran 1991: 83). Certain geog transformations, such as mass migration, and waves of refugees and asylum seekers—a consequence of the colonial expansion—and the post-Socialist reconfiguration of nation- meant that the study of diasporas and cosmopolitan identities had to take into consider historical and cultural specificities. These configurations mark the move towards “a nom in which the very parameters of specific historical moments are embodied and ... are sca and regrouped in new points of becoming” (Evans-Braziel and Mannur 2008: 3). This vo joins and enriches an existing debate from which new, provincialized conceptualizations

cosmopolitanism have emerged, such as “critical cosmopolitanism” (Rabinow 1986), “postcolonial cosmopolitanism” (Parry 1991), “rooted cosmopolitanism” (Cohen 1992; Ackerman 1999), “nomadic subjects” (Braidotti 1994), “discrepant cosmopolitanism” (Clifford 1992), “vernacular cosmopolitanism” (Bhabha 1996; Beckenbridge et al., 2000; Werbner 2006; Gunew 2001), “patriotic cosmopolitanism” (Appiah 1998), “border cosmopolitanism” (Mignolo 2000), “borderline cosmopolitanism” (Spivak 1999; Gilroy 2004), “banal cosmopolitanism” (Beck 2002), “subaltern cosmopolitanism” and “cosmopolitan legality” (De Sousa Santos and Rodríguez-Garavito 2007), “indigenous cosmopolitanism” (Goodale 2006; Forte 2010), “emancipatory cosmopolitanism” (Pieterse 2006), “ordinary cosmopolitanism” (Kendall, Woodward, and Skrbis 2007), “postcolonial cosmopolitanism” (Bhambra 2011; Baban 2016), “Cosmopolitan Europe” (Horta and Robbins 2003; Pichler 2009; Ponzanesi 2018), “libidinal cosmopolitanism” (Boston 2016), and “aesthetics of cosmopolitanism” (Titley 2005).

Is the multiplication into various inflections of “cosmopolitanism” (Horta and Robbins 2003) an undermining of the very notion of cosmopolitanism itself and an attempt to save the notion from its Eurocentric origin? For the editors, the triumph of the descriptive plural over the normative singular opens up as many questions as it answers (Horta and Robbins 2017). The plural is a celebration of the particulars, but also a way out of the positive/negative, center/periphery, normative/descriptive binarism. It is not simply the celebration of a new form of cosmopolitanism from below, but the awareness that we are now capable of perceiving attachment to distant others in ways that were not possible in the past. The editors mention Boltanski in their introduction, referring to a new idea of common humanity, which makes suffering, or the attachment to distant people, possible through new features of modern humanitarianism. According to Lilie Chouliaraki, whose work has elaborated on Boltanski’s reference to media and spectatorship, “the representation of proximity/distance to the suffering” is therefore part of “the analytics of mediation” or *The Spectatorship of Suffering*, one of her books is titled (2006: 8). The reading of Chouliaraki is relevant to the shift in the notion of cosmopolitanism theorized in the 1990s and more recently as it implies significant changes in the structure of feeling and thinking beyond the nation as allowed by new technologies and digital media culture. This new form of universalism is very much defined by and through mediated encounters between different places and “worlds”. Chouliaraki rightly states that the question of solidarity (...) cannot be examined separately from the communicative structure that has made this discourse available to us in the first place” (2013: 15). It is through these mediated encounters with mediated suffering that we share a sense of common humanity (as proposed by Boltanski 1999 and Sontag 2003). Through empathy with unfortunate others, we can also scrutinize how these cosmopolitan imaginaries are circulated. The rise of digital technology and social media complements more traditional forms of communication, leading to enhanced possibilities to forge bonds of solidarity between different worlds (including through func

and humanitarian campaigns).

Chouliariaki’s *The Ironic Spectator: Solidarity in an Age of Post-Humanitarianism* (2013) on her previous work on the mediatization of distant suffering, and states that forms of solidarity have changed substantially in recent decades in tandem with the shifts in media, technology, markets, and politics. Solidarity, she states, is not based on pity with distant Others any more (as Boltanski had argued), rather it is based on self-fulfillment, a self-oriented morality that centers around doing good to Others based upon “how I feel” (2-3). As Christensen and Jansson write, the moral and *post*-humanitarian subject of cosmopolitanism emerges as a narcissistic agent that is self-benefitting, and acts in order to just fulfil their own self-gratifying vision rather than acting and engaging politically (Christensen and Jansson 2015: 4) Though this volume does not engage with media perspectives on cosmopolitanism, there is an engagement with cosmopolitanism as an unfinished business that remains, as Robert Young writes in his contribution to this volume, between national sovereignty and cosmopolitanism. “Can the state [...] stretch itself to protect the mobile, migratory, multiply-loyal subjects that nationalism has excluded but that are now so characteristic of our time? It is only in such embodied forms that Young suggests, that the cosmopolitan idea truly exists—if indeed cosmopolitanism exists as such an idea rather than a pressing series of unanswered and perhaps unanswerable questions” (13). Robert Young asks “How can we translate the cosmopolitan idea into a transformative reality?” (140). “The question presupposes that, even if we seek to describe actually existing shapes and spaces, cosmopolitanism remains for us a strenuous aspiration” (16). James Clifford’s idea of discrepant cosmopolitanism, mentioned above and discussed by Robbins and Cheah’s *Cosmopolitics*, foregrounds the notion of cosmopolitanism not as an elitism but as applicable also to the servants, maids, guides, and translators who accompanied educated travelers and explorers as they moved through cosmopolitan hubs.

Cosmopolitanism was not only for gentlemen travelers, but it applied also to the people who were the servants of those travelers, who had their own specific cosmopolitan view of the world. Even the organized coercion of people produces “cosmopolitan workers.” This challenges the notion that certain classes of people are cosmopolitan (travelers) while the rest of us are not (natives). Questions of power aside, “they” and “we” can no longer be divided into local and cosmopolitan. (Clifford 1992: 107-8) For the poor, the experience of cosmopolitanism can be at times more an experience of loss than of luxury but it can also refer to more popular forms of cosmopolitanism, such as the cosmopolitanism encountered in the Brazilian *favelas*, that can account for a more vibrant and innovative articulation of cosmopolitanism from below. The cosmopolitanism of the poor as theorized by Silviano Santiago in the context of Afro-Brazilian culture is a way of subscribing to the multiple(s) contained in the notion of cosmopolitanism as a form of resistance to mainstream culture as well as the reality of the postmodern megacity.

that are serviced by those poor ethnic and socially marginalized groups. But the culture poor finds expression in other cosmopolitanisms and transnational cultural forms too, such as *Kizomba*, an African word meaning an encounter of identities, which is now becoming a hype around the world. Originating in Angola, it was transmitted through slavery and brought to Brazil to transfer further in modern times from the global south to the north, many *Kizomba* festivals abound. *Kizomba* has moved away from its roots in a history of pain and suffering to become a celebration of multicultural consumption (Kabir 2013).

Cosmopolitanisms is full of complex negotiations between what the term cosmopolitanism meant in its overused history and the obligations it has for its future aspiration. As Robbins points out in his chapter on “George Orwell, Cosmopolitanism, and Global Justice,” cosmopolitanism is still pretty much about our obligations to others, not only in “emotional terms, by suffering with them, but also as an economic recognition of the need for a redistribution between rich and poor (the rich having clearly benefitted from the poor in symbolic, and ideological ways) if we think global justice means pushing for a more equitable distribution of the world’s material resources. The question Robbins poses is a central one: “Is it possible to see the new cosmopolitanism as also a redistributive cosmopolitanism?” (43)

The waning of the nation-state and the rise of transnational neoliberal models has also meant the collapse of the welfare state (at least for those countries that actually had one) and with it the erosion of national solidarity and, in tandem, international solidarity. This connects to David Hollinger and his “Cosmopolitanism and the Problem of Solidarity,” which goes beyond the color divide. For Achille Mbembe, “Afropolitanism” is the cosmopolitan awareness of African origin, which rejects the essentialist and nativist discourse of Negritude and Pan-Africanism. Afropolitanism is also not just about being in the diaspora and a classy African citizen of the world (see figures such as Teju Cole or Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, Taiye Selasi or No Vuyo Bulawayo, often included in the new generation of glossy representatives of the African diaspora); it is more about a poetic and aesthetic that implies the multitudes of black people without necessarily doing away with the politics of oppression and the violence inflicted on the continent and their people. But Afropolitanism or “Afropolitism” is more about Africans in Africa, who experience several “worlds” and develop a new transnational culture that draws on multiple legacies and rewrites African modernity. This is further elaborated by Emma Dabiri in her “The Problems and Pitfalls of Afropolitanism” in which she lays out her reservations about the term and the various debates and responses to the embracing or rejection of the new fashion. Though empowering and clearly celebratory, the term, which seems to have been used for the first time in 2005 by Taiye Selasi, reeks of neoliberal ideology. In this chapter, Dabiri distinguishes herself from Achille Mbembe’s position on Afropolitanism, which according to him is a way of renouncing pernicious racialized thinking in favor of more fluid and interconnected identities (along the lines of Gilroy’s *Black Atlantic* and his rejection of “black race” as a unifying category (Gilroy 1993). Mbembe is also critical of the idea of African tradition, as such a mythological

reminds us of Fanon’s warning against the pitfalls of nationalism. Yet Dabiri’s reservations about the consumeristic nature of Afropolitanism, seen as a boutique for African commodities in intellectual attire, remain. The Afropolitan class (or elite class) replicates so many of the clichés and privileges associated with old European notions of cosmopolitanism; furthermore, how does it contribute to the improvement of conditions on the African continent and the salvaging from the rapacious operations of the IMF and World Bank? This is of course the warning that Ellis Cashmore gave in his book *The Black Cultural Industry* (1997): the commodification of hip-hop and rap has not meant financial revenues for either the black or their surroundings, but primarily income for the record labels, often controlled by white people. Moreover, the consumption of “black music” has not automatically fostered cultural integration or understanding among different groups but, as Cashmore writes, has created a cordon sanitaire around the dangers and risks of blackness by consuming, at a safe distance, some of its products and spirit (Cashmore 1997). This is also Paul Gilroy’s position. He has argued that commodification has destroyed what was wonderful about black culture to the advantage of corporate interests, though he still sees the contradictions and potentiality as a unique transmitter of cultures across diaspora (Gilroy 1993, 2011).

If, for Dabiri, Afropolitanism is too glossy, polite, and compromised by its associations with business and capitalism, and too much a digestible narrative of Africa rising that the West is willing to promote and embrace, we should not forget that Afropolitanism is not homogeneous itself, and following the adoption of the plural in cosmopolitanisms, we might dare to add in its plural form, Afropolitanisms. Even though it may not be an alternative to Adichie’s “not a single story” and is too close to African narratives of Afro-pessimism and poverty, it is also something that should not be denied the power of resistance and criticism just because of its “stylistic” embracement of a “hipster” African experience. As I argued elsewhere, the postcolonial cultural industry is not just about the fashionability of Third World culture on sale. It is a way of striking back by at times “formally” abiding by the rules of the marketplace while undermining the very system from within (Ponzanesi, 2014). It would be unfair to disregard the impact of writers such as Chimamanda Adichie and her critique of Western visions of race and African identities as merely cool and trivial because of her great popularity and success with Western readers. This would lead the debate back to the diatribe between Wole Soyinka (who won the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1986) and Chinweizu, who claimed that Soyinka had become a true representative of the African continent but because he had applied enough “Africanesque patina and inlays to satisfy Western tourist taste for exotica” (in Gibbs and Lindfors 1993: 346). The decision to give the first Nobel Prize in Literature for an African writer to Soyinka rather than the much older Senghor, father of the Negritude movement, was interpreted as the Swedish Academy’s preference for a postcolonial, avant-gardist and therefore globally more palatable writer over the old, anti-colonial, black nationalist, and francophone

writer. Besides reflecting the competition between two linguistic centers, Paris and London was also due to the anti-colonial struggle's loss of traction in the new era of rampant globalization. The debate between Mbembe and Dabiri has wider implications not only for the idea of Afropolitanism but also for the recent uprising in South Africa with the Rhodes Must Fall movement. Monuments of European heritage were attacked and libraries were burned as a knowledge stemming from the West and from the Empire was seen as ideologically tainted and oppressive. However, as Achille Mbembe responded (2016), to burn Western books is not enough to decolonize the university and start all over with a clean slate. He notes that history is not the same as memory and that we cannot just erase history; we should engage with memory as a way of putting history to rest, especially histories of suffering, trauma, and victimization (Mbembe 2016: 30). I believe that this current take on cosmopolitanism, from the global to the local, can contribute to a revamping of the term, not for purely intellectual and academic practice but to initiate new economic mobilities that would have otherwise not been possible. In his contribution, "Accra's Cosmopolitan Constellations," Ato Quayson brings the world to Africa in a way that reverses the claim of Afropolitanism as Africans being diasporic in the world. He argues that instead, the cities in the global south are shown as not only the new metropolises, but also as places where new forms of cosmopolitanism(s) take place and materialize through an urban and scriptural economy: billboards, posters, advertisements contributing to a mixing of oral and written imported traditions, now hybridized and shaped anew. What Quayson argues is that Accra has always been a place of transnational connections, and the interconnectedness of cultures has been going on for a very long time. He claims that "The world of Facebook, and Gollywood is but one instalment of this continuing transnationalism" and that despite the usual claims of Africa as the underbelly of the world, people in Africa have the same "capacity for reimagining the world as do people born in Mississauga, or New Jersey, or Bromley or London" (219). Talking about the Afro-Brazilian returnees from Bahia to Accra (Tabon) in the nineteenth century, as a group of Africans from the faraway lands of enslavement, the process of settling into their new homeland was far from smooth, underlining the fact that even in Africa ethnicity and multiraciality can give rise to xenophobia and conflict. If this still makes cosmopolitanism a requisite of the middle classes and transnational groups, then cosmopolitanism has little to offer on a local level. However, if cosmopolitanism becomes a choice among the many identities available, some of which are deeply ethnic, then it can be considered part of the constellations that are already intrinsic to African culture and future imaginations. The quizzical afterword by Anthony Appiah shows this through a personal anecdote. Appiah's complex extended family is an example of a globally interconnected world. Appiah's notion of cosmopolitanism remains anchored in the idea of dialogue and conversation across cultures, in order to reach if not agreement at least fair conditions for disagreement. Appiah's notion of cosmopolitanism is something we cannot escape. In addition to the invocation of cohabitation and conversation as the only way forward to rescue cosmopolitanism, I would invoke the figuration of connection

also raised by Craig Calhoun in his chapter on “A Cosmopolitanism of Connections.” “We heard many times that we now live in an interconnected world, but what does that mean exactly? That we all have Wi-Fi? That we all live in a platform society? That we all watch the same Netflix series? That we live in a borderless world?” As Calhoun writes: “We are connected but incompletely” (198). We have responsibilities because of these connections, which are specific and others, and are not just marked by abstract similarities. The specificities for these interactions vary according to the individual, cultural context, and historical period, so connections are not abstract figurations. Therefore, cosmopolitanism is not only about the mobility of the privileged, or the forced mobility of the disadvantaged, but about specific connections that position us in the world, and function at different scales, from the local to the global. And because of digital connectivity we can navigate different worlds at the same time; we belong to different constituencies without renouncing either the local, or the national or the global. It is in the hypertextual embrace of multiple paths that cosmopolitanisms might offer opportunities for thinking and feeling beyond methodological nationalisms.

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[1] Bob Dylan, "The Times They Are A-Changin'" (1964).

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